

4D PRINTING OF COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents results from an investigation on the process to develop composite rotors using 4D printing of composites. The process only requires the laying of flat composite prepregs on a flat mold, yet upon curing, curved and twisted rotors can be obtained. The rotor has two blades with curvature to provide fluid pumping action. The effects of different parameters on the final configuration of the rotor are examined.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the advent of 3D printing, many structures with complex geometries can be made. The process is done by additive manufacturing where layer after layer of the material are deposited. The material used is usually low strength plastic materials either in the form of powder or liquid. The locations where the material is deposited is controlled by a computer program. Some mechanism for the solidification of the material (such as laser heating for curing) is subsequently done. While this process represents significant advances in the concept for manufacturing, it is fairly slow. What is meant by 4D printing is that simple layers of materials with special deformable characteristics are added at strategic locations to make flat structures. Subsequently when the structure is subjected to an activation source such as heating, lighting, or absorption of some liquid such as water, the structure is deformed into the special complex geometries. Figure 1 shows a few pieces of complex geometries made by 4D printing.

Figure 1: Examples of pieces made by 4D printing [1, 2]

For composites, additive manufacturing can be done using automated tape laying or automated tape placement machines. Composite layers of different orientations can be deposited one on top of the other. In addition, within each layer, the fibers can be steered such that the fiber direction can be changed from

place to place within the same plane of a layer. Flat stacks of thermoset composites can be made. These are then subsequently cured in an autoclave or in an oven (for the case of out-of-autoclave prepregs). Depending on the arrangement of the fibers within the stack, the final piece will have different configuration. By performing deformation analysis taking into account residual constraints due to shrinkage and/or thermal loads, the deformed shape of the piece can be predicted. Using this procedure, one can design the fiber configuration in a flat stack of prepregs such that subsequent to the curing of the matrix, the piece will assume a certain desired configuration to be determined at the outset. Figure 2 shows curved pieces made of carbon/epoxy composites, using automated fiber placement and autoclave cure.

Figure 2: Curved composite pieces

2. ANALYSIS TO DETERMINE THE DEFORMED CONFIGURATION

Since the laminates made from 4D printing are relatively thin, laminate theory can be used to determine the radius of curvature and the deformed configuration due to curing and due to cooling from cure temperature to room temperature. The formulation to determine the radii of curvature has been given in [3]. The analysis for the deformation is given below.

Relation between curvatures and out-of-plane displacement:

$$\kappa_x = -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2}$$

$$\kappa_y = -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2}$$

$$\kappa_{xy} = -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y}$$

(1)

Integrating the first of equation (1) gives:

$$w = -\frac{1}{2}\kappa_x x^2 + f_1(y)x + f_2(y) \quad (2)$$

Integrating the second of equation (1) gives:

$$w = -\frac{1}{2}\kappa_y y^2 + g_1(x)y + g_2(x) \quad (3)$$

Differentiating equation (2) with respect to x and then with respect to y gives:

$$\kappa_{xy} = -\frac{df_1}{dy} \quad (4)$$

Differentiating equation (3) with respect to y and then with respect to x gives:

$$\kappa_{xy} = -\frac{dg_1}{dx} \quad (5)$$

Equating two equations (4) and (5) gives:

$$f_1 = -\kappa_{xy}y + c \quad (6)$$

and

$$g_1 = -\kappa_{xy}x + c \quad (7)$$

Substituting equations (6) and (7) into (2) and (3) gives:

$$w = -\frac{1}{2}\kappa_x x^2 - \kappa_{xy}xy + cx + f_2(y) = -\frac{1}{2}\kappa_y y^2 - \kappa_{xy}xy + cy + g_2(x) \quad (8)$$

Matching terms gives:

$$w = -\frac{1}{2}\kappa_x x^2 - \frac{1}{2}\kappa_y y^2 - \kappa_{xy}xy \quad (9)$$

Equation (9) gives the out-of-plane displacement for any point on the surface of the laminates.

Discussion

Even though equation (9) shows that the three curvatures contribute to the out-of-plane displacement w , observation of the deformed shape of laminates made of [0/90] stacking sequence (where $\kappa_{xy} = 0$) shows that the laminate can only bend along one curvature at a time. Figure 3 shows the configuration of the laminate when it bends along one curvature. What this means is that for this laminate, only one curvature (either κ_x or κ_y) exists at any one time. Pushing the laminate in the out-of-plane direction will make the laminate to snap from one curvature to the other. As such the equation for the out of plane displacement is given either by equation (10a) or 10b) as:

$$w = -\frac{1}{2}\kappa_x x^2 \quad (10a)$$

$$w = -\frac{1}{2}\kappa_y y^2$$

(10b)

Figure 3: Cured laminate configuration for [0/90] stacking

If one were to plot the out-of-plane displacement w as a function of the coordinate x , a parabola is obtained as shown in figure 4. However this does not agree with the experimental configuration as shown in figure 3. This is not the correct way to plot w as a function of x . Instead, the coordinate axis needs to be updated. This can be understood by incremental plotting as follows (Figure 5): From the origin O of the coordinate x , a point P_1 at coordinate Δx from the origin O is selected. A corresponding w_1 is determined using either of equation (10). The point P_1 now has a new position of point P'_1 . The coordinate axis OP_1 is now changed to OP'_1 . Now along OP'_1 , another increment Δx will locate a new point P_2 . Another corresponding w_2 is determined using either of equation (10). This will determine the position of point P'_2 . The coordinate now is updated from P'_1P_2 to $P'_1P'_2$. The process continues similarly. The accuracy of the final result depends on the size of the increment Δx . Smaller increments will provide more accurate results.

Figure 4: Plotting out of plane displacement w as a function of x (unit in inches)

Figure 5: Updating of coordinate axes

Following this incremental plotting procedure, the deformed configuration for the laminate is shown in figure 6, which agrees with that in figure 3.

Figure 6: Plotting out of plane displacement w using updated coordinate axes.

3. DEVELOPMENT OF COMPOSITE ROTORS

One possible application for the 4D printing of composites is composite rotor. The rotor can be used to pump fluid or it can be used to transform the flow of fluid to drive shafts. The orientation of the fibers in the composite can be tailored to provide different degrees of curve and twist. Two different configurations are presented below.

Rotor with bending curvature only:

The lay up arrangement for the flat laminate to make this type of rotor is shown in figure 7. The boundary of the hashed area represents the boundary of the layers at each level. For example, for level 1, first the 0 layer is laid down on the right (from B to F). Then the 90 layer is placed on the left with an overlap of 1 inch on top of the 0 layer (from C to A). The overlap provides connection between the left and right sides and prevents failure of the laminate under centrifugal action. The middle section of the laminate has the lay up sequence [0/90/0/0/90/0] which is symmetric to assure flatness for mounting on the shaft. The right hand side has the lay up sequence [0₃/90₃] and the left side has the lay up sequence [90₃/0₃]. This unsymmetry provides the curved configuration. The profile of the edge of the rotor after curing is shown in figure 8.

Figure 7: Lay up arrangement for rotor with bending curvature only

Figure 8: Edge profile of rotor with bending curvature only.

Rotor with twist:

In order to make a rotor with a good degree of twist, fiber steering was utilized. Figure 9 shows the lay up arrangement for this type of rotor. The shaded area represents the fiber steering area. Fiber steering is shown in figure 9. In figure 8, there are overlaps to provide resistance against centrifugal action. For example, for level 1, first the 0 layer is placed on the right side of the laminate (from C to F). Then the second 0 layer is placed from D to A. This layer is also steered within the region CB so that its fiber orientation changes from 0° to 45°. For the remaining distance BA, the fiber orientation stays at 45°. The middle part of the laminate has 12 layers and it is a symmetric laminate, while each of the right

and left sides has 6 layers. The right side has the lay up sequence $[0_3/45_3]$ while the left side has the sequence of $[45_3/0_3]$. The unsymmetry provides the twist to the rotor.

Figure 10 shows a photo of this rotor.

Figure 8: Lay up arrangement for rotor with twist

Figure 9: Fiber steering

Figure 10: Photo of rotor with twist.

4. ROTATION TESTS

As a preliminary investigation on the performance of the different composite rotors, these rotors were mounted on an electric motor for rotation tests. Figure 11 shows this configuration. The torques required of the motor to run these rotors at a certain speed were measured. The torques were determined as the product of current input and the speed of rotation. Table 1 shows the results.

Figure 11: Composite rotor on shaft for motion test.

	Speed (rpm)	Torque (N.m)
Without rotor	1830	5
Rotor 1	1830	6.5
Rotor 2	1830	9.13

Table 1: Torques for the different rotors

The torque associated with motor running alone without rotor is 5 N.m. With rotor 1 (11 inch in diameter) having only bending curvature, the torque increased to 6.5 N.m. With rotor 2 (16 inch in diameter) with bending and twisting curvature, the torque went up to 9.13 N.m. A part of this increase is due to the larger diameter of rotor 2, and a part of that is due to the addition of twist. It is not clear at this point how much is the percentage of each.

5. CONCLUSION

The concept for 4D printing of composites has been introduced. The analytical procedure for the determination of the shape of laminates made of 0/90 type of stacking sequences has been proposed. Lay-up sequences for two types of composite rotors have been presented. The results show promising results in which composite structures of complex shape can be produced by laying up flat stacks of prepregs, without the need for complicated molds. The final shape takes place due to the unsymmetric behavior of the material.

The use of the rotor as an application for 4D printing of composites is only an example. Other applications using this concept can also be developed and this is the subject for future work.

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7. REFERENCES

1. Deng D., Chen Y., "Origami-based self-folding structure design and fabrication using project based stereolithography". *ASME J. Mech. Des.*, 2015, 137(2): 021701-021701-12.
2. Kwok T.H., Wang CCI., Deng D., Zhang Y., Chen Y., "Four-dimensional printing for freeform surfaces: Design optimization of origami and kirigami structures", *ASME J. Mech Des.*, 2015: 137 (11): 111413-111413-10.
3. Hoa Suong V., "Factors affecting the properties of composites made by 4D printing (moldless composites manufacturing)", *J. Advanced manufacturing: Polymer and composites science*, submitted, March 2017.